

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea *Part IX. Diammine Bis 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea Cobalt(III) Complexes**

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Unstable, yellow coloured cobalt(II) bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes have been oxidised in presence of ammonia to stable rose-red coloured diammine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes. The ligands are found to undergo protonation to different extents resulting in salts of different ionic natures. Equivalent weights have been determined and aqueous conductances evaluated to verify the ionic natures. Chemical evidence points to a *trans* disposition of the two ammonia groups. Spectral measurements are also reported, which show two bands typical of $3d^6$ cobalt (III) complexes.

For 1-amidino-o-methylurea (AMUH), the complexes described are of the following types:

(1) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})_2] \text{X}$ aq., (2) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})] \text{X}_2$ aq. and (3) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \text{X}_3$ aq. (where X = a univalent anion). Similar complexes have also been isolated for other 1-amidino-O-alkylurea ligands.

Some years ago a discovery was made of a reaction between dicyandiamide and alcohols in the presence of copper(II) acetate, leading to the synthesis of a new class of organic co-ordinating ligands¹. The authors had earlier described these as guanylalkylureas¹. However, since 1959, many significant studies have been carried out on the synthesis^{2,3}, structure^{3,4}, kinetics of formation⁵ of these newly synthesized ligands and the ligands are truly named as 1-amidino-O-alkylureas instead of guanylalkylureas or 1-amidino-3-alkylureas. In a number of communications the co-ordination complexes of copper(II),⁶ nickel(II)^{7,8}, palladium(II)⁹, oxo-vanadium(IV)¹⁰, chromium(III)¹¹, zinc(II)¹²

*Earlier parts in the series appeared under "Guanylalkylureas and their metallic complexes". Recent researches have necessitated this change into 1-amidino-O-alkylureas.

A preliminary note covering synthesis of some complexes of this paper and the several other following papers, have appeared (R.L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 1965, **27, 2447). A summary of these works was presented before the joint convention of the Indian Chemical Society and the C.S.I.R. held at Aligarh Muslim University, December 25-29, 1965.

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1. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499.
2. R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 789; 1961, **38**, 689.
3. G. D. Diana, E. S. Zalay and R. A. Culter, Jr., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 298.
4. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *this Journal*, 1967, **44**, 560.
5. W. A. Baker and M. Daniels, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1194.
6. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 567.
7. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 576.
8. V. Rasmussen and W. A. Baker., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 580.
9. R. L. Dutta, B. Sur and N. R. Sengupta, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 565.
10. R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 863.
11. R. L. Dutta, B. Sur and N. R. Sengupta, *Science and Culture*, 1959, **25**, 381.
12. M. M. Ray and B. Sur, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 798.

and boron(III)¹³ have been reported. The reactions of co-ordinated 1-amidino-O-alkylureas have also been studied¹⁴. A report concerning cobalt(III) tris chelate complex, the only one so far on cobaltic complexes, had also appeared¹⁵.

Continuing our investigations on the donor properties of these fascinating co-ordinating ligands, we will now describe in a number of communications the syntheses, properties and reactions of a series of bis-1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes. Incidentally, this constitutes the first report on a bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complex.

Cobalt (II) salts react with 1-amidino-O-methylurea (hereinafter abbreviated as AMUH) in the presence of ammonia to precipitate the yellow cobaltous complex $[\text{Co}(\text{AMU})_2]$. This compound appears to be stable only in a dry atmosphere and we will have occasions to look into its properties in a forthcoming paper. The yellow cobaltous complex, however, readily undergoes oxidation to cobalt(III) stage, in the presence of ammonia, adding on two ammonia ligands to complete the octahedral structure around cobalt. The constitutions of the complexes are such that H^+ elimination occurs from one of the NH groups and classical co-ordination is effected from one other NH_2 group. The free NH_2 group can be further utilised for salt formation through protonation. In these diammino cobaltic 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes, we have come across a varied degree of protonation. Thus, when cobalt(II) chloride (1 mole), 1-amidino-O-methylurea (2-mole) sulphate are treated with ammonia and the mixture oxidised by leading in a brisk stream of air, the first crop of crystals that appear, has the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})_2] \text{Cl}$. aq; evidently the two 1-amidino-O-methyl-urea ligands are in unprotonated form. The complex reacts alkaline but is not in the form $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}$ in as much as the complex provides a molar conductance value of a uni-univalent electrolyte (144.7 mhos). Dissociated OH ions must have given rise to a very high conductance value indeed. Equivalent weights of the various complex species were determined by running the aqueous solution through a H^+ form cation exchanger (Amberlite IR 120) and titrating the liberated acid with standard NaOH . Equivalent weight, on its own, is not capable of differentiating between such alternative formulations as $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU}_2)] \text{Cl} \cdot \text{X} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{OH})_2 \text{Cl} \cdot \text{X} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as in the latter case, passage through H^+ cation exchanger will produce the same one mole HCl as in the former case. However, conductance results are more straight forward and on the basis of the ionic natures deduced from the conductance values, we have checked the calculated equivalent weights of the different complex species we obtained in this series of studies with the experimentally obtained values. The second crop that appears on addition of spirit to the filtrate of the above preparation, analysed as $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})] \text{SO}_4$. The complex provides a molar conductance value of a bi-bivalent electrolyte. Thus the alternative formula of a hydroxide sulphate is ruled out and that one of the two 1-amidino-O-alkylurea molecules has gone over to the protonated form. The above sulphate salt is obtained as the sole product when cobalt(II) chloride is replaced in the above reactions by cobalt(II) sulphate. Both of these salts can be further protonated by the action of dilute acids to produce the final form $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \text{X}_3$ (X =a univalent anion). This registers a molar conductance value of a tri-

13. A. N. Maitra and D. Sen, The Joint Convention of the Chemical Research Committee, C. S. I.R. and Society of Biological Chemists, India, Sec. B-4, p. 3.

14. S. N. Poddar and J. N. Adhya, Private Communication.

15. R. L. Dutta, B. Sur and N. R. Sengupta, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 573.

univalent electrolyte and an equivalent weight corresponding to a third of the molecular weight. The filtrate from the preparation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})]\text{SO}_4$, still containing enough ammonia, on prolonged aeration (as long as 60 hours) loses all excess ammonia, turns slightly acidic and finally throws down orange red crystals of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \text{ aq.}$ Continued aeration did not provide the hydroxo-aquo bis 1-amidino-0-methylurea cobalt(III) with the discharge of the two co-ordinated NH_3 groups. Concentration at which the preparation was conducted, seems to have some inevitable effect in that at very dilute solutions (0.001M) there was definite spectral evidence that the co-ordinated ammonia groups have totally or partially undergone hydrolytic rupture. This failure to obtain the hydroxo-aquo complex in the solid state, is contrary to the ready replacement observed originally^{16,17} and also in our Laboratory¹⁸ with the diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) complexes. A series of salts (namely chloride, bromide, iodide, thiocyanate, oxalate, thiosulphate etc.) of the above complex cations of varying positive charge (due to the different degrees of protonation of the ligands) have been prepared and characterised. A few salts containing mixed anions such as chloride dinitrate have also been prepared. These salts lend support to the stability of the variedly protonated species of the ligands in these complexes.

A surprising reaction is noticed in that the freshly prepared ammonia-free bis 1-amidino-0-methylurea cobalt(II) dissolves readily in the cold in a strong, aqueous ammonium thiocyanate solution with evolution of ammonia and producing a deep red-violet solution, which on standing for some time deposits crystals of diammine bis

CHART I

Synthesis and reactions of diammine bis (1-amidino-0-methylurea) cobalt (III) complexes.

16. P. Ráy and A. N. Mazumdar, *this Journal*, 1946, **23**, 73.

17. P. Ráy and S. P. Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1942, **19**, 1.

18. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *this Journal*, 1967, **44**, 832, 842, 853.

1-amidino-O-methylurea thiocyanate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})](\text{SCN})_2^*$. This result was contrary to our expectation of a diisothiocyanato bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) complex. The reaction is novel in the sense that similar interaction does not occur in the presence of potassium thiocyanate and a few drops of ammonia added deliberately but does go when NH_4^+ ion is also present. The exact nature of the complex was established through elemental analysis and conductance studies and the peculiar observation was followed up and broadened by the use of a few other 1-amidino-O-alkylurea ligands.

TABLE I
Equivalent Weight Values

Complex	Found	Required*
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})_2] \text{Cl} \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	410	404
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})] \text{SO}_4$	213	210
3. $(\text{CO}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2) (\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	164	168
4. $(\text{CO}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2) \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	170	161
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH}_2)] \text{Cl} \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	190	180
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	172	164
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] (\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$	160	166
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})_2] (\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	190	180

AMUH=1-amidino-O-methylurea; AEUH= 1-amidino-O-ethylurea;

APⁱUH = 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea.

*These values have been deduced on the basis of elemental analysis and conductance measurements.

We would now like to comment on the variation of conductance with dilution. The values increased steadily with dilution and the final values are much above the expected range (Λ_m for 1 : 1 electrolyte 96-115 mhos, Λ_m for 1:2 electrolyte 225-270 mhos, Λ_m

TABLE II
Electrolytic conductance studies at 33.5°C

Complex	Dilution (litres)	64	128	256	512	1024
		Λ_v	117.0	126.0	139.1	148.0
		Λ_∞	147.3	152.5	157.0	161.4
		Λ_∞ (mean)	158.8 mhos			
		Λ_m	476.4 mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹			
			Equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution		Molar conductivity.	
			mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹		mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹	
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})_2] \text{Cl} \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$			144.7		144.7	
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})_2] \text{I}$			143.8		143.8	
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMU})(\text{AMUH})] \text{SO}_4$			162.0		324.0	
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$			160.0		480.0	
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEU})(\text{AEUH})] (\text{SCN})_2$			146.4		292.8	
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \text{I}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$			150.3		450.9	
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AP}^i\text{U})(\text{AP}^i\text{UH})] \text{I}_2$			144.5		289.0	

Λ_∞ was calculated from Λ_v from Walden formula.

* $\Lambda_\infty = \Lambda_v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ where n_1 is the valency of the cation and n_2 is the valency of the anion.

*With the methyl derivative the reaction is faster than with the other ligands, so that much of the complex is precipitated even before filtration is possible

for 1 : 3 electrolytes 380-432 mhos, and Λ_M for 2 : 2 electrolytes 250 mhos¹⁹). We feel that both hydrolytic dissociation as well as the high temperature prevailing at the time of measurements have contributed to these high conductance values. In the case of trans $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the value for Λ_{1024} was found to be 177.8 mhos¹⁶ at 33°C, whereas our corresponding value is 165.5 mhos at 33.5°C for the methyl derivative (BigH = a molecule of biguanide).

A complex such as diammine bis 1-amidino-0-alkylurea cobalt(III) can exist as geometrical isomers. Based on the chemical evidences, we believe, the present complex belongs to the trans configuration. Though chemical evidences are not always unequivocal, nevertheless the following reactions are revealing. The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \text{X}_3$ (X = a univalent cation, e.g., Cl^-) provides in the cold rose red oxalato salt $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{OX})_{1.5}$. This complex on heating on a steam bath loses ammonia and deposits an intense violet oxalato bis 1-amidino-0-methylurea cobalt(III) oxalate. When we refer to the cis and trans diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) complexes, for which both the cis and trans geometrical isomers are known, we find that the cis isomer readily yields in the cold an intense violet oxalato bis biguanide cobalt(III) oxalate, whereas the trans variety in the cold provides the rose red oxalato salt only, though on heating the trans complex too gives the oxalato-oxalato salt^{16,17}. Evidently warming initiates trans-cis isomerisation followed by the introduction of the oxalato group. Besides, we have examined the reaction of our products with a variety of other powerful bidentate ligands. With none of these ligands, namely, o-phenanthroline, dipyriddy etc., there occurs any evolution of ammonia at room temperature. Evolution of ammonia occurred with all of them around 60°C resulting in the formation of the mixed heterochelates, $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{AMUH})_2]^{+n}$ (where AA = o-phenanthroline etc.). Action of such bidentate ligands on cis and trans diammine bis biguanide Co(III) also reveals a comparable difference¹⁸. The cis hydroxo-aquo bis biguanide Co(III) reacts with thiosulphate in the presence of a trace of dilute acetic acid in the cold to produce a green μ -thiosulphato complex¹⁷. The 1-amidino-0-alkylurea complexes have not yielded such green coloured, thiosulphato bridged complex. Such thiosulphato bridged complex apparently is not of sufficient stability in the 1-amidino-0-alkylurea series. In an attempt to obtain the other variety of the diammine complex (presumably cis), we did vary the methods of preparation. Thus the yellow cobalt(II) complex was treated with ammonia and oxidised by H_2O_2 in the cold and a pure base and sulphate were isolated and characterised. We then checked up the spectra of the two sulphates obtained by the two different methods and observed that these two provided spectra which are superimposable. Both the spectra have two absorption bands located at 335-340 m μ and at 486-505 m μ which are typical of six coordinate Co(III) complexes^{19,20}. Thus we have so far got hold of only one variety of the diammine complex and spectral study has been of no help in characterising this species as cis or trans isomer. Of the two absorption bands in Co(III) complexes, $[\text{CoA}_4\text{B}_2]$ the higher wave length one would be split in the trans species. However, this would happen only if the two ligands are well enough separated in the spectrochemical series^{20,21}. Since we do not expect much variation in the ligand field strength of ammonia and the 1-amidino-0-alkylureas, this is not unreasonable that the spectra has not been split. In this context this may be mentioned that two geometrical isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2][\text{n}_2]^{+3}$ also do not reveal any reasonable variation in their spectra²¹, though trans $[\text{Co en}_2\text{F}_2]^+$, trans $[\text{Co en}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]^+$ and trans halogeno ace-

19. M. M. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, 1964, p-254.

tato tetramine group of complexes do show the splitting^{20,22,23}. This has been possible because the ligands are very much widely separated in the spectrochemical series than those are in the present case.

We desired to check up whether it is at all possible to effect any resolution of the complex in question. With that end in view attempts were made to isolate the chloride-tartrate or the pure d-tartrate or the d-camphor sulphonate of the complex cation, which could then be subjected to fractional crystallisation. Unfortunately we have not succeeded in crystallising any of the above salts. In this connection it may be mentioned that cis-diammine bis biguanide Co(III) chloride-d-tartrate has been resolved into optical isomers via the hydroxo-aquo complex¹⁸.

TABLE III

Electronic absorption spectral studies

Complex	Band II		Band I	
	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Molar absorptivity litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Molar absorptivity litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1. [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMU) ₂] Cl.2.5H ₂ O	30,000	630	{ 20,400— 20,000	70.0
2. [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMU) (AMUH)]SO ₄	30,000	450	{ 20,000— 19,600	85.0
3. (a) [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O*	{ 30,00— 29,400	157	{ 20,600— 19,800	75.5
(b) [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O**	{ 30,000— 29,400	157	{ 20,0600 19,800	75.5
4. [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] I ₃ .2H ₂ O	{ 33,000— 30,000	300	{ 20,600 19,800	102
5. [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AP ⁱ U) (AP ⁱ UH)] I ₂	30,000	625	{ 20,400 20,000	145

*Obtained by air oxidation method.

**Obtained by H₂O₂ oxidation method.

We have also recorded the electronic absorption spectra of all other different types that we have so far synthesised. In all cases, the spectra shows two bands and no further splitting was observed. The spectral characteristics are recorded in Table III. Some of the short wave length bands show a rather high molar extinction coefficient, which might be ascribed to absorption by other components present in the system. Besides, the absorption spectra of the diammine bis l-amidino-0-alkylurea Co(III) sulphate on storing changes its visible colour from light red to distinct violet. This was reflected in a profound change in the nature as also in the molar absorptivity of the short wave length band in particular. We believe this is due to a change of the diammine complex to one of a hydroxo-aquo type. Similar spectral change was noted in the case of the corresponding l-amidino-0-

20. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, 'Advanced Inorganic Chemistry,' Interscience Publishers Inc., New York 1962, p-729.

21. C. K. Jorgensen, 'Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding,' Pergamon Press, 1962, p-293.

22. K. Kuroda and P. S. Gentile, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 155, 1289; *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1965, **38**, 1368.

23. V. Carunchio, G. Grassini-Strazza, G. Ortaggi and C. Padiglione, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 841

ethylurea derivative and is believed to be a general occurrence in the series of these ligands. This property is also very much in line with the corresponding bis biguanide complexes¹⁸. We plan to undertake detail kinetic studies on this transformation.

Besides the methyl derivative, many other 1-amidino-0-alkylurea complexes have also been synthesised and adequately characterised, details of which are included in the Experimental. The solubility of the diammine complex increases with the increase in the chain length of the alkyl group, which is in contrast with the dipyridine complexes (to be described in the next part) and cobalt(III) tris 1-amidino-0-alkylurea complexes.¹⁵

The complexes described in this communication are assigned tentatively the following trans structures, taking the methyl derivative as the representating ligand.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-0-methylurea, 1-amidino-0-ethylurea, 1-amidino-0-n-butylurea and 1-amidino-0-isobutylurea sulphates* were prepared and purified according to published methods¹, 1-amidino-0-isopropylurea sulphate was not characterised earlier. This was prepared by a similar procedure. {Found: SO₄, 25.08; N, 29.2 (AB¹UH)₂SO₄ requires SO₄, 25.20; N, 29.0 percent}.

The complexes described below are in general soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol and acetone. Unless otherwise mentioned all these complexes were dried in air.

1. *Diammine-bis-1-amidino-0-methylurea cobalt(III) mono chloride*: CoCl₂·6H₂O (2.4 g) and 1-amidino-0-methylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (15 ml), liquor ammonia (10 ml) added and a brisk current of air was passed for one hour in the cold, during which period the yellow cobalt(II) bis 1-amidino-0-methylurea was oxidised to a dark red solution followed by the appearance of rose-red crystals. These were filtered and washed with spirit. [Found: Co, 14.78; N, 35.0; Cl, 8.6; H₂O (by loss at 90°C), 11.0. [Co(NH₃)₂

*AB¹UH=1-amidino-0-isobutylurea and AB²UH=1-amidino-0-n-butyl urea.

(AMU)₂] Cl. 2.5 H₂O requires Co, 14.69; N, 34.8; Cl, 8.8; H₂O, 11.1%. The substance reacts alkaline to litmus.

2. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono sulphate* CoSO₄.7H₂O (2.8 g) and 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (15 ml) and liquor ammonia (10 ml) added. The mixture with the yellow cobaltous complex was then oxidised by passing a brisk current of air for one hour. The rose-red crystals formed were filtered and washed with spirit (yield 2 g). From the filtrate another crop (yield-2 g) was obtained by the addition of spirit in the cold {Found: Co, 14.4; N 33.6; SO₄, 23.0 [Co(NH₃)₂ (AMU) (AMUH)] SO₄ requires Co, 14.2; N, 33.33; SO₄ 22.85%}. The substance reacts alkaline to litmus. This can be redissolved in warm ammoniacal water and precipitated in the cold by the addition of spirit.

3. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono-iodide* (Brownish red) was prepared by the action of a concentrated solution of KI on that of the complex mono-chloride. {Found: Co, 13.03; N, 31.28; I, 28.6. [Co(NH₃)₂ (AMU)₂] I requires Co, 13.11; N, 31.11; I, 28.22%}.

4. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea mono bromide* (rose red) and 5. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono thiocyanate*: (brownish red) were prepared by the action of concentrated solution of KBr or NH₄SCN respectively on that of the complex mono chloride. (Found: Co, 14.40; N, 34.5; Br, 19.5. [Co(NH₃)₂ (AMU)₂] Br requires Co, 14.6; N, 34.7; Br 19.8 and Found: Co, 14.8; N, 39.0; SCN, 14.0; H₂O (by loss at 90°C), 4.9. [Co(NH₃)₂(AMU)₂] SCN, H₂O requires Co, 14.78; N, 38.6; SCN, 14.5; H₂O, 4.7%).

6. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) tri chloride*: The diammine mono chloride (1 g) was suspended in water (5 ml), cooled in ice and was neutralised with 2N HCl to pH 6.7. The colour changed from rose red to orange. The crystals were filtered and washed with spirit. From the filtrate a further amount may be obtained by the addition of spirit. (Found: Co, 12.3, N, 29.1; Cl, 22.0. [Co(NH₃)₂ (AMUH)₂] Cl₃.3H₂O requires Co, 12.1; N, 28.8; Cl, 21.8%).

7. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate* (orange) was prepared from the mono sulphate by neutralisation with 2N H₂SO₄ in the cold. (Found: Co, 12.0; N, 27.7; SO₄, 28.8; H₂O (by loss at 90°C), 6.9. [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂](SO₄)_{1.5}. 2H₂O requires Co, 11.75; N, 27.7; SO₄, 28.5; H₂O, 7.1%). This gives a neutral reaction.

8. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride di nitrate* (orange) was prepared from 1 by neutralisation with dilute HNO₃. (Found: Co, 11.2; N, 29.9; Cl, 6.69; [Co(NH₃)₂ (AMUH)₂]Cl(NO₃)₂. 3 H₂O requires Co, 10.96; N, 30.1; Cl, 6.7%).

9. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) perchlorate* (orange glistening flakes) was prepared from the diammine mono chloride by neutralisation with dilute HClO₄ in the cold. (Found * N, 22.26. [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂] (ClO₄)₃ requires N, 22.47%). This gives a neutral reaction.

10. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite* (yellow glistening flakes) was prepared by double decomposition of the corresponding tri-sulphate with

*Cobalt analysis was not possible due to explosion of the complex.

$\text{Na}_3 [\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$. (Found: Co, 18.0; N, 34.1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] [\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ requires Co, 17.87; N, 33.9%).

The corresponding tri-iodide and tri-bromide were prepared by double decomposition of the tri-chloride with saturated solution of KI and KBr respectively.

11. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) tri iodide* (Brownish-red) (Found: Co, 8.5; N, 20.20; I, 53.6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{I}_3$ requires Co, 8.38; N, 19.8; I, 54.1%).

12. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) tri bromide* (Rose red) (Found: Co, 9.9; N, 23.4; Br, 40.2; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Br}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 9.8; N, 23.29; Br, 39.95%).

13. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) thiosulphate*. The diammine tri-chloride was dissolved in minimum amount of water and to this was added a concentrated solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$. Orange red shining crystals began to appear. The mixture was cooled in ice for few hours, filtered and washed with spirit. (Found: Co, 11.3; N, 26.50; S_2O_3 , 32.2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.1; N, 26.35; S_2O_3 ; 31.7%) An attempt to prepare the bridged thiosulphate compound from this failed.

14. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) oxalate*. To a suspension of the diammine mono-chloride (0.5 g) in water (5 ml) a solution of oxalic acid (0.25 g) in water (5 ml) was added in the cold. The mixture was allowed to stand for an hour with occasional stirring. The orange crystals were filtered and washed with spirit. (Found: Co, 11.88; N, 28.7; C_2O_4 , 26.4; $[\text{Co} (\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.9; N, 28.4; C_2O_4 , 26.7%).

15. *Oxalato bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) oxalate*. The diammine mono-chloride (0.5 g) and oxalic acid (0.25 g) were mixed in water (15 ml) and warmed on a steam bath. The colour of the solution gradually changed from orange to deep violet and ammonia was disengaged; when the evolution of ammonia ceased the solution was cooled and deep violet crystals separated. This compound was also obtained by heating the aqueous solution of the complex oxalate salt (as prepared above) at the temperature of steam bath. This is sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol and acetone. (Found: Co, 13.8; N, 25.8; H_2O (by loss at 110°C), 2.5 $[\text{Co} (\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.5} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 13.6; N, 25.9; H_2O , 2.0%).

16. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt (III) di thiocyanate*. The yellow cobaltous complex was filtered, washed and was treated with a saturated solution of NH_4SCN . The cobaltous complex was oxidised at once to a pink solution. This was immediately filtered and cooled in a refrigerator for one day. Rose red crystals were filtered and sucked dry. (Found: Co, 12.5; N, 35.5; SCN, 24.7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMU}) (\text{AMUH})] (\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 12.3; N, 35.2; SCN, 24.3%). The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

17. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) hydroxide*. $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.8 g) and 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (3.6 g) were dissolved in water (10 ml) and liquor ammonia (10 ml) added. The yellow cobaltous complex formed was filtered quickly and oxidised by H_2O_2 (20 vol, 2 ml) in presence of liquor ammonia (15 ml) to a dark red solu-

tion. This was filtered and to the filtrate acetone (100 ml) was added with stirring in the cold. The rose red crystals separated were filtered, washed with acetone and dried in a desiccator over KOH. (Found: Co, 12.7; N, 30.3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMU})_2] (\text{OH}) \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 12.6; N, 30.0%).

The complex base was dissolved in minimum amount of water and neutralised with $2\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_4$ in the cold to give diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate. (Found: Co, 11.9; N, 28.0; SO_4 , 28.1; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.75; N, 27.7; SO_4 , 28.5%).

18. *Dicyano bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III)*: The diammine mono sulphate was treated with excess of KCN solution. The colour changed from rose red to yellow indicating the formation of dicyano compound. The mixture was then heated on a steam bath for few minutes, cooled and filtered. To the filtrate acetone was added and kept in the frigidaire for few days. The yellow crystals separated were filtered, washed with ice cold acetone and dried in a desiccator. This compound was previously prepared from cobalt(III) tris 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate¹⁵. (Found: Co, 16.9; N, 40.8. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2 (\text{AMU}) (\text{AMUH})]$ requires Co, 17.2; N, 40.9%).

19. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) sulphate* was prepared similarly as for the methyl derivative but here oxidation was carried out for two hours to form a dark red solution. Ammonia was allowed to evaporate under a fan and then neutralised with $2\text{N H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Acetone was added in the cold. An oil formed was washed by decantation with cold aqueous acetone and crystals obtained by addition of more acetone and repeated scratching. (Found: Co, 12.0; N, 28.4; SO_4 , 29.4. $[\text{Co} (\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AEUH})_2] (\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ requires Co, 11.87; N, 28.1; SO_4 , 29.0%). This reacts neutral to litmus.

20. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) chloride* was prepared similarly as for the methyl derivative using 1-amidino-O-ethylurea chloride¹ (3.3 g), but the red solution formed was filtered off, ammonia was allowed to evaporate under a fan and neutralised with 2N HCl . Rose red crystals were obtained by repeated addition of acetone and scratching. (Found: Co, 11.0; N, 25.7. Cl, 19.4. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AEUH})_2] \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10.7, N, 25.5; Cl, 19.3%).

21. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) iodide* was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of KI to the dark red solution of the chloride as obtained above and cooling in a frigidaire for one day. (Found: Co, 7.8; N, 17.9; I, 50.0. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AEUH})_2] \text{I}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 7.6; N, 18.1; I, 49.5%).

22. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) bromide* (Brown) was prepared as for the iodide using a solution of KBr instead of KI. (Found: Co, 10.0; N, 24.0; Br, 40.2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AEUH})_2] \text{Br}_3$ requires Co, 9.9; N, 23.7; Br, 40.4%).

23. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite* (Yellow) was prepared by double decomposition of the corresponding sulphate with a concentrated solution of $\text{Na}_3 [\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$. (Found: Co, 17.3; N, 32.8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 (\text{AEUH})_2] [\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ requires Co, 17.1; N, 32.5%).

24. *Oxalato-bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) oxalate*: The dark red solution of the complex base obtained similarly as the methyl derivative was neutralised with oxalic

acid. The complex oxalate salt could not be isolated due to the extreme solubility. The solution was heated on a steam bath. After the complete evolution of ammonia, the solution was cooled and deep-violet crystals separated. The compound is sparingly soluble in water. (Found: Co, 12.4; N, 23.1; H₂O (by loss at 110°C), 7.5 [Co(C₂O₄) (AEUH)₂] (C₂O₄)_{0.5}, 2H₂O requires Co, 12.1; N, 23.0; H₂O, 7.3%).

25. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) di thiocyanate* was obtained by following a procedure similar to that of the methyl derivative. This is pink and shining. (Found: Co, 12.4; N, 36.4; SCN, 24.8. [Co(NH₃)₂ (AEU) (AEUH)] (SCN)₂ requires Co, 12.6; N, 36.0; SCN, 24.8%). The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

26. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) sulphate*: The cobaltous complex obtained from 3.8 g of 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea sulphate was oxidised in presence of liquor ammonia (10ml) by passing a current of air for 4-5 hours. This was then treated as for the ethyl derivative. The substance is highly soluble in water. (Found: Co, 10.5; N, 26.0; SO₄, 26.2. [Co(NH₃)₂ (APIUH)₂] (SO₄)_{1.5} H₂O requires Co, 10.8; N, 25.7; SO₄; 26.5%).

27. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) di iodide*: (Brownish red): The dark red solution of the complex base as obtained above was neutralised with dilute HCl and a concentrated solution of KI was added and cooled in the frigidaire for one day to have the crystals. The substance is soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: Co, 9.5; N, 22.0; I, 40.5. [Co(NH₃)₂ (APIU) (APIUH)] I₂ requires Co, 9.3; N, 22.0; I, 40.6%).

The following complexes were prepared by adopting similar procedures as for the corresponding O-ethyl derivatives.

28. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) di thiocyanate* (Rose) (Found: Co, 12.0; N, 34.3; SCN, 24.0. [Co(NH₃)₂ (APIU) (APIUH)] (SCN)₂ requires Co, 11.8; N, 34.0; SCN, 23.4%). The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

29. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite* (Yellow) (Found: Co, 16.6; N, 31.29. [Co(NH₃)₂ (APIUH)₂] [Co(NO₂)₆] requires Co, 16.4; N, 31.28%).

30. *Oxalato bis 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) oxalate* (Violet) (Found: Co, 11.1; N, 21.0; H₂O (by loss at 110°C), 10.2. [Co(C₂O₄) (APIUH)₂] (C₂O₄)_{0.5} 3H₂O requires Co, 11.0; N, 21.0; H₂O, 10.1%). The complex oxalate was not isolable due to extreme solubility in water.

31. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea cobalt(III) di thiocyanate* (Rose red) (Found: Co, 11.3; N, 32.0; SCN, 22.5. [Co(NH₃)₂ (ABU) (ABUH)] (SCN)₂ requires Co, 11.2; N, 32.0; SCN, 22.1%). The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

32. *Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea cobalt(III) di iodide*. The red solution of the above thiocyanate was filtered to a concentrated solution of KI. The mixture was cooled in ice. The rose red crystals separated were filtered and washed with ice cold water. The compound is soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: Co, 8.0; N, 18.6; I, 34.2 [Co(NH₃)₂ (ABU) (ABUH)] I₂ .5H₂O requires Co, 7.8; N, 18.6; I, 33.8%).

33. *Oxalato bis 1-amidino-O-n-butylurea cobalt(III) oxalate* (Violet). The substance is

sparingly soluble in water. (Found: Co, 11.8; N, 22.4 [$\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{AB}^n\text{UH})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_{0.3}$ requires Co, 11.6; N, 22.1%]).

Analytical Methods:—Cobalt content was determined by decomposing the complex to cobalt oxides by ignition and then treating with concentrated HNO_3 and HCl and finally with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Cobalt was finally weighed as anhydrous cobalt sulphate.

Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Duma's combustion technique. Anions were estimated by usual methods.

Absorption spectra were recorded with the help of a Hilger Watts Uvispeck Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells and conductance with a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell.

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